

Smart prosthetic socket with vibrotactile feedback and sEMG sensing

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Abstract— This work reports the development of a transfemoral prosthetic socket equipped with a bidirectional interface. The socket is made up of a rigid structure embedded into a silicone matrix. Three vibrotactile units and four pairs of surface EMG (sEMG) electrodes are integrated at the interface with the residual limb to enable the user's motion intention decoding and returning sensory feedback. This novel design aims to improve the user's comfort while facilitating the integration of smart components at the residual tissue interface. Experimental results demonstrated the feasibility of the proposed approach, thus opening new possibilities for the bidirectional control of robotic prostheses.

Keywords—prosthetic socket, residual limb, sEMG sensing, transfemoral amputation, vibrotactile feedback.

I. INTRODUCTION

In robotic limb prostheses, a closed human-centered control loop is an essential requirement for the achievement of an intuitive and tight integration of the artificial device with the user. In this regard, surface electromyographic (sEMG) signals have the potential to allow for effective voluntary control of the prosthesis through non-invasive sensors combined with machine-learning-based algorithms [1]. VibroTactile (VT) feedback has demonstrated promising results in restoring lost sensory information in lower limb amputees [2]. However, the integration of smart components at the socket level (i.e., the prosthetic physical human-machine interface) is still a stated challenge, particularly in more proximal amputation levels, such as transfemoral. Indeed, the socket is a rigid structure that replicates the user's residual limb shape to create a grip on bony prominences and a suction effect on residual tissues [3]. The socket applies high stresses on tissues, often resulting in dermatological issues and pain. Thus, the integration of additional components can further affect the prosthesis's comfort and suspension.

In this work, a novel socket is proposed to enable a bidirectional interface for active transfemoral prostheses (Fig. 1). The device is based onto a mechatronic design to enable a stable and comfortable biomechanical coupling with the residual limb, while facilitating the integration of sensors and actuators in contact with the residual tissues. More technical details of this solution can be found in [4].

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II. DESIGN OVERVIEW

Fig. 1. Smart socket with sEMG sensing and vibrotactile feedback. The socket features a rigid structure integrated into a silicone matrix. Three vibrotactile units driven by a control unit and four pairs of clip electrodes connected to a sEMG detection system are integrated into the socket in contact with residual tissues.

The proposed socket is constituted by a carbon-fiber-reinforced resin structure that covers the residual limb distal end and extends proximally only at lateral and medial sites (Fig. 1). This rigid structure is integrated into a silicone matrix, thus resulting in a more flexible design with respect to traditional full-rigid sockets. In particular, the new socket can passively compensate for small volume increases of the residual limb over time while guaranteeing a stable biomechanical coupling. In addition, the inner silicone layer avoids the need for a standalone prosthetic liner (i.e., a soft silicone sock usually worn on the residual limb and under the socket to reduce pressures on tissues), thus simplifying the integration of smart components at the interface with tissues.

A previously proposed EMG-based intention detection algorithm exploiting a Support Vector Machine (SVM) approach has demonstrated that strong performances can be obtained by analysing only a sub-window of the gait cycle and with a limited number of recording sites (i.e., four sites:

Rectus Femoris, Tensor Fasciae Latae, Adductor Longus, and Biceps Femoris) [1]. Based on this evidence, the socket has been equipped with cables and clip connections for attaching four pairs of surface pre-gelled clip electrodes. The cables are connected to a commercial EMG detection system (Sessantaquattro, OT Bioelettronica S.r.l.) mounted on the outer surface of the socket. The clip connections allow for an easy integration and replacement of the electrodes on the target muscles.

Concerning the augmenting feedback, three VibroTactile (VT) units were integrated at the lateral, anterior, and medial proximal sites of the socket, in contact with the residual tissues. The VTs were placed more than 2 cm from the electrodes to avoid disturbances on the EMG signals. Each VT unit consists of an eccentric rotating mass (ERM) motor (Pico Vibe 304-116, Precision MicroDrives) embedded into a 20 mm large and 6 mm thick PDMS silicone disk [5]. The VT stimuli are delivered by a control unit, namely *VibroBoard*, equipped with a real-time sbRIO-9651 controller (National Instruments) endowed with a Xilinx Zynq-7020 System on Chip. Each VT unit is driven by a 1 kHz PWM (Pulse-Width Modulation) of a 5V source. The *VibroBoard* is encased in a wearable plastic box fastened on a waist belt and it was designed to be easily combined with the control system of an active prosthesis, as well as the EMG detection system. Future efforts will deal with the design of a single and compact electronic board to be integrated into the distal part of an active prosthetic device [6].

A transfemoral amputated subject was recruited for the development of a custom-made socket prototype (design study approved by the Joint Ethical Committee of Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna and Scuola Normale Superiore; Approval no. 11/2021). The manufacturing was carried out at the prosthetic center Franchi Ortopedia (Cascina, PI, Italy). The rigid structure was manufactured by an expert prosthetist through the traditional lamination technique, whereas the silicone substrate was realized by means of custom molds. The inner silicone layer was designed with a variable thickness that gradually increases from 5 mm proximally to 15 mm distally, mimicking commercial prosthetic liners. The smart components were integrated during the manufacturing by using specific templates, positioned on the residual limb cast of the subject. The socket prototype is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Smart socket with four sEMG sensors and three vibrotactile units (medial view, left; lateral view, center; socket worn by the recruited subject, right). A commercial unidirectional valve was exploited for the suction suspension of the socket on the residual limb.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION AND RESULTS

To demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed approach, a circuit training including five different locomotion tasks (i.e., ground level walking, ramps ascending, ramps descending, stairs ascending, stairs descending) was performed 15 times by the recruited subject. The sEMG signals of the target muscles were acquired during the 0% - 60% sub-window of the gait cycle and the classification output of the ongoing step was evaluated by the linear-kernel SVM [1]. The decoded task classification accuracy was found equal to 86.84% (IQR: 10.42%). In the future, the combination of the sEMG signals with the output of IMU sensors, which can be easily integrated on the outer surface of the prosthesis, can allow for further improvements in the detection of the user's intent before the actual movement.

A psychophysical test was carried out by randomly activating one, two, three, or no VT units at three different stimulation intensities (i.e., 2g, 3g, and 4g ERM motor peak acceleration) and then asking the subject to identify the stimulus position. Each condition was repeated 4 times and the test was performed 5 times in a standing position. Results revealed that vibration stimuli from a single VT unit and at 3g acceleration were the best-perceived and assessed the feasibility of equipping the prosthetic interface with a vibrotactile feedback system. In the future, the exploitation of sensorized shoes will allow for the synchronization of the haptic stimuli with the gait events to improve the user's temporal gait symmetry [2].

Finally, the subject pointed out a Socket Comfort Score of the new system equal to 8/10, which provided preliminary evidences of the acceptability of the proposed system.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The integration of smart technologies in wearable physical interfaces is still an open issue due to the many parameters that can affect the device comfort and ergonomics. This is particularly challenging in lower limb prostheses, where the physical interface constituted by the socket is a critical bottleneck, featured by a low satisfaction level reported by the majority of amputees. In this context, the design of a bidirectional interface based on a non-invasive approach that focuses on the integration of sensors and actuators into a transfemoral prosthetic socket was pursued. Promising results were obtained in terms of perceived vibrotactile stimuli and functionality of an EMG-based intention decoding approach, as well as positive feedback in terms of comfort.

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